

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New 2-(Heteroaryl)vinylsulphonyl Derivatives[†]

D. R. SHRIDHAR*, C. V. REDDY SASTRY, A. K. MARWAH,
(Miss) PADMA PARIHAR and K. B. LAL

Chemistry Division, IDPL Research Centre, Indian Drugs and Pharmaceuticals Limited, Hyderabad-500 037

Manuscript received 26 December 1984, accepted 31 July 1985

Several new 2-[(5-nitro-1-methyl-2-imidazolyl-, 5-nitro-2-furyl-, and 5-nitro-2-thienyl)vinyl]-*N*-arylsulphonamides and sulphonyl heterocycles (1 and 2) have been prepared and screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial, antifungal, antiamoebic, antitrichomonal and *in vivo* anthelmintic activities, against a variety of microorganisms. Some of the compounds possess promising antibacterial, antiamoebic and antitrichomonal *in vitro* activities.

RECENTLY we have reported¹ the synthesis and biological activity of a large number of heteroarylvinylsulphonamide derivatives possessing nitrofuran and nitrothiophene ring systems as heteroaromatic moiety. It was observed that some of the compounds in this series possess significant antibacterial, antifungal, antiamoebic, antitrichomonal and anthelmintic activities. Various biological activities, such as antiparasitic, antiamoebic, antitrichomonal *etc.* have been associated with nitroimidazole moiety². Furthermore, several 5-nitro-1-substituted-imidazolylvinyllogues³ have been reported to exhibit marked antibacterial and antiprotozoal properties. In view of these and in continuation of our ongoing synthetic work on this biologically interesting heteroarylvinyls, it was thought of interest to prepare some new heteroarylvinylsulphonyl derivatives of types 1 and 2 carrying 5-nitro-1-methylimidazole residue (X=N, Y=NCH₃), and to evaluate their biological activities.

Various 2-[(heteroaryl)vinyl]-*N*-arylsulphonamides (1) reported herein were prepared according to the procedure described earlier¹ by reaction of the different heteroaldehydes with appropriate arylaminosulphonylacetic acid in acetic anhydride-sodium acetate, followed by acid hydrolysis (dioxane-H₂SO₄) of the resulting 2-heteroarylvinyl-*N*-arylsulphonamide acetates. 2-[(1-Methyl-5-nitro-2-imidazolyl)vinyl]-*N*-sulphonyl heterocycles (2) were synthesised in a similar manner by treatment of 5-nitro-1-methyl-2-formylimidazole with the corresponding heterocyclic-*N*-sulphonylacetic acid (Scheme 1).

The structures of all the new compounds reported in Table I were based on their method of synthesis, elemental analyses, ir spectra exhibiting characteristic absorptions at 1610 (C=C), 1340 and 1120 cm⁻¹ (SO₂), and nmr spectra in TFA, which

showed a pair of AB doublets, accounting for one proton each centered around δ 6.8-7.2 (*J* 15 Hz) and 7.5-7.7 (*J* 15 Hz) for *trans*-vinylic protons.

Scheme 1

Biological activity: All the heteroarylvinylsulphonyl derivatives reported were tested *in vitro* for (i) antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S.a*), *Streptococcus faecalis* (*S.a*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*Ps.a*), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K.p*) and *Vibrio cholerae* (*V.c*), (ii) antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* (*C.a*), *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (*T.m*), *T. rubrum* (*T.r*), *Microsporium canis* (*M.c*) and *Histoplasma capsulatum* (*H.c*), (iii) antiamoebic activity against *Entamoeba histolytica* SLF-4 (*E.h*) and (iv) antitrichomonal activity using fluid thioglycolate medium against *Trichomonas vaginalis* (*T.v*) and *Trichomonas foetus* (*T.f*) by methods described earlier⁴ (Table I). Com-

[†] Communication No. 84 from IDPL Research Centre, Hyderabad.

TABLE 1—HETEROARYLVINYLSULPHONYL DERIVATIVES (1 AND 2)*

Compd. no.	Ar/R	M.p., °C	Yield %	Molecular formula*	Biological activity ** (µg ml ⁻¹)												
					Antibacterial				Antifungal				Antiamoebic				Antitrichomonal
					S. a	S. f	Ps. a	K. p	V. c	C. a	T. m	T. r	M. c.	H. c	E. h	T. v	T. f
1.	C ₆ H ₅	168	68	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	5	25	50	>100	10	>100	100	100	50	100	2.5	1	>100
2.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	187	61	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₄ S	2.5	>100	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	100	>100	2.5	100	>100
3.	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	148	54	C ₁₃ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₄ S	2.5	25	50	2.5	>100	>100	50	100	50	100	1.25	100	>100
4.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	178	66	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	2.5	10	50	>100	10	>100	>100	>100	50	>100	5	1	>100
5.	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	120	81	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₅ S	2.5	25	50	2.5	5	>100	>100	50	>100	5	1	>100	
6.	3-CF ₃ C ₆ H ₄	149	62	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	5	50	>100	5	>100	>100	>100	>100	10	25	10	100	>100
7.	3-NO ₂ 4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	172	32	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	5	10	50	2.5	50	>100	>100	>100	100	10	10	0.1	0.1
8.	2-Cl,4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	195	55	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	10	1	1
9.	4-C ₆ H ₅ SC ₆ H ₄	145	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	2.5	2.5	10	2.5	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	10	0.01	0.1
10.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ CHC ₆ H ₄	119	34	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	2.5	25	50	5	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	5	0.01	0.01
11.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ CHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	130	49	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	1	5	25	1	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	5	0.01	0.01
12.	4-C ₆ H ₁₁ C ₆ H ₄	171	51	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	20	6.25	-
13.	3-NO ₂ 4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	176	59	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	10	10	50	10	5	>100	>100	25	25	>100	10	1	0.5
14.	2-Cl,4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	207	46	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	50	100	10	10	25	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	25	2	5
15.	4-C ₆ H ₅ SC ₆ H ₄	121	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	5	10	25	10	25	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	10	10	100
16.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ CHC ₆ H ₄	126	68	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	10	50	100	5	10	>100	>100	2.5	>100	>100	25	10	50
17.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ CHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	90	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	25	25	>100	25	10	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	10	10	20
18.	4-C ₆ H ₁₁ C ₆ H ₄	162	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	10	25	>100	25	10	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	20	10	50
19.	3-NO ₂ 4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	153	39	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	5	10	25	2.5	25	>100	25	25	10	>100	20	1.5	>100
20.	2-Cl,4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	221	37	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₅ S	50	25	50	50	10	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	50	0.1	10
21.	4-C ₆ H ₅ SC ₆ H ₄	112	76	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	25	100	100	10	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	25	2	5
22.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ CHC ₆ H ₄	138	88	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	5	5	25	2.5	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	20	1	1
23.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ CHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	126	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	2.5	5	>100	2.5	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	25	2	5
24.	4-C ₆ H ₁₁ C ₆ H ₄	181	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	1	50	50	1	2.5	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	10	1	1
25.	(CH ₃) ₄	181	15	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ S	100	>100	100	100	10	>100	>100	>100	50	100	1.25	1	1
26.	(CH ₃) ₅	191	15	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	50	100	>100	50	25	>100	100	50	10	25	2.5	1	1
27.	(CH ₃) ₅ -O-(CH ₃) ₂	192	40	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₅ S	25	50	>100	50	10	>100	>100	>100	>100	100	1.25	1	>100
28.	(CH ₃) ₅ -SO ₂ (CH ₃) ₂	244	38	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆ S	25	50	>100	50	10	>100	>100	>100	>100	100	10	1	>100
29.	(CH ₃) ₅ -SO ₂ (CH ₃) ₂	255	56	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆ S	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	100	1	>100
30.	(CH ₃) ₅ -SO ₂ -(CH ₃) ₂	251	29	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆ S	25	25	100	25	25	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	25	-	5

* All the compounds were analysed for C, H and N and the analytical results are within ± 0.4% of the theoretical values.

** All the compounds were also tested for antibacterial activity against *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus vulgaris*, and antifungal activity against *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Microsporium gypseum* but found to be inactive.

(-) - Not tested.

pounds showing considerable antiamebic and antitrichomonal activities *in vitro* ($10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were further tested *in vivo* against simultaneous hepatic and intestinal infections of golden hamsters by *E. histolytica* SLF-4, and against *T. vaginalis* and *T. foetus* infections in mice at $4 \times 300 \text{ mg/kg}$ (p.o.) dose. Representative compounds were also tested for their anthelmintic activity in mice against *Hymenolepis nana* at $1 \times 500 \text{ mg/kg}$ (p.o.), *Nematospiroides dubius* at $4 \times 500 \text{ mg/kg}$ (p.o.), *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in rats at $3 \times 250 \text{ mg/kg}$ (p.o.) and against *Ancylostoma ceylanicum* (hamster-adopted dog strain) at $2 \times 250 \text{ mg/kg}$ (p.o.) dose in hamsters as described earlier⁵.

Several compounds reported in the present paper were found to possess marked antibacterial activity *in vitro*, particularly against gram +ve bacteria with mic values ranging from $1.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ as compared to that of $25\text{--}200 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ by nitrofurantoin. Thus, compounds 2-5, 9-11, 23 and 24 were found to be active against *S. aureus* at $1\text{--}2.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, while compounds 9, 11, 22 and 23 inhibited the growth of *S. faecalis* at 2.5 to $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Amongst the gram -ve bacteria employed in the screening, *K. pneumoniae* and *V. cholerae* were found to be more susceptible than the others with the mic values ranging from $1\text{--}5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for compounds 3, 5-7, 9-11, 13, 16, 19, 22 and 23. None of the compounds displayed any noteworthy antifungal activity *in vitro* excepting 13, 16 and 19 which inhibited the growth of *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum* and *M. canis* at $2.5\text{--}25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. In the *in vitro* antiamebic screening several compounds (1-5, 10, 11, 25-27) exhibited significant activity against *E. histolytica* SLF-4 at $1.25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ but were found to be inactive in the *in vivo* studies. In the antitrichomonal *in vitro* testing compounds 1, 4, 5, 7-13, 20, 22, 25-28 against *T. vaginalis*, and 7-11, 13, 20, 23, 25 and 26 against *T. foetus* showed highest activity with minimum lethal concentrations (mlc) ranging from 0.01 to $1.0 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. However, these compounds were found to be inactive in the *in vivo* studies when tested in mice. None of the compounds tested, possess any significant anthelmintic activity.

The biological screening results of the present studies indicate that there is little improvement in the biological activity profile of these heteroarylvinylsulphonamides and sulphonyl heterocycles by incorporation of nitroimidazolyl moiety in place of nitrofuran and nitrothiophene residues.

Experimental

2 - [(1 - Methyl-5-nitro-2-imidazolyl)vinyl]sulphonanilide, 1 (1): A mixture of 1-methyl-5-nitro-2-formylimidazole (1.7 g, 0.011 mol), phenylamino-sulphonylacetic acid (2.15 g, 0.01 mol) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (25 ml) was heated with stirring at $75 \pm 5^\circ$

for 4 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into ice-water, and the liberated crude material was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution followed by water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent yielded the *N*-acetyl derivative of 1 which was recrystallised from chloroform to give a pale yellow crystalline solid (1.42 g , 45%) m.p. 180° .

A solution of the above *N*-acetyl derivative (2.0 g) in dioxane (20 ml) containing 12.5% sulphuric acid (v/v) was refluxed for 4.5 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water and extracted with chloroform. The organic layer on usual working up gave the crude title product, which was recrystallised from chloroform-hexane to furnish pure title compound (1) as pale yellow crystalline solid (1.2 g, 68%), m.p. 168° (Found: C, 46.86; H, 3.93; N, 18.58. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 46.76; H, 3.90; N, 18.18%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3260 (NH), 1595 (C=C), 1525, 1370 (NO_2), 1345 and 1150 cm^{-1} (SO_2); δ (TFA) 3.80 (3H, s, NCH_3), 7.1 (1H, d, J 15Hz, vinyl proton), 7.43 (1H, d, J 15Hz, vinyl proton), 6.77-7.00 (5H, m, ArH) and 8.00 (1H, s, proton of the imidazole ring).

Compounds 2-24 (Table 1) were prepared in a similar manner by reaction of appropriate heteroarylaldehyde with the corresponding arylamino-sulphonylacetic acid.

1-[2-(1-Methyl-5-nitro-2-imidazolyl)vinyl]sulphonylpyrrolidine, 2 (25): A mixture of 1-methyl-5-nitro-2-formylimidazole (3.41 g, 0.022 mol), 1-pyrrolidine-sulphonylacetic acid (3.86 g, 0.02 mol) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1.62 g, 0.02 mol) in acetic anhydride (50 ml) was stirred at 70° for 2 h and at $120 \pm 5^\circ$ for another 4 h. The reaction mixture was worked up as described in the previous experiment to yield the product as yellow crystalline solid which was recrystallised from CHCl_3 -ether to give pure title compound (25) (0.9 g, 15%), m.p. 191° (chloroform ether) (Found: C, 42.17; H, 5.20; N, 19.20. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 41.96; H, 4.89; N, 19.54%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1610 (C=C), 1325 and 1130 cm^{-1} (SO_2); δ (TFA) 1.5-1.7 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 2.9-3.1 (4H, m, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.87 (3H, s, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 7.15 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, vinyl proton), 7.35 (1H, d, J 15Hz, vinyl proton) and 8.00 (1H, s, proton of imidazole ring).

Compounds 26-30 were similarly prepared from the corresponding heterocyclisulphonylacetic acids and heteroarylaldehydes.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. G. S. Reddi, Dr. Lovekar and staff of Biology Division of this Centre for biological screening. Thanks are also due to the staff of analytical laboratories for elemental analyses and spectral data.

References

1. D. R. SHRIDHAR, C. V. REDDY SASTRY, K. B. LAL, A. K. MARWAH, G. S. REDDI, K. K. BHOPALE, H. N. TRIPATHI, R. S. KHOKHAR, K. TRIPATHI and G. S. T. SAI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 234.
2. S. T. ANDREW in "Medicinal Chemistry", ed. A. BURGER Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1969, Vol. 1, p. 573.
3. W. J. ROSS, W. B. JAMIENSON and M. C. McCOWEN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 1035 ; 1973, 16, 347.
4. D. R. SHRIDHAR, P. GOPAL REDDI, S. R. MOORTHY, O. P. MADAN, M. JOGIBHUKTA, C. JANAKIRAM, K. K. BHOPALE, K. TRIPATHI, G. P. DATTA and S. R. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 17, 483.
5. D. R. SHRIDHAR, K. SRINIVASA RAO, K. K. BHOPALE, H. N. TRIPATHI and G. S. T. SAI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 699.